

INVESTIGATING MEDICINAL ATTRIBUTES: BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF BONSUPARI (CARYOTA URENS L.) FRUITS

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Abstract: *Caryota urens L.*, commonly known as the Fishtail palm or Bonsupari in Bengali, is a plant with diverse medicinal properties. Traditionally utilized for treating gastric ulcer, migraine, rheumatic swellings, snake bites, and tooth ailments, this plant has garnered attention for its therapeutic potential. Recent scientific investigations have revealed the nutritional richness of *C. urens* sap, which contains a mixture of simple sugars such as sucrose, glucose, and fructose. Additionally, flavonoids have been isolated from the methanol extract of its fruits. Moreover, research conducted in recent years has unveiled the significant antioxidant, anti-diabetic, and anti-microbial activities exhibited by *C. urens*. With its roots deeply embedded in traditional medicine and promising scientific evidence supporting its medicinal properties, *C. urens* emerges as a valuable resource in the realm of natural medicine. This paper aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the medicinal attributes of *C. urens*, highlighting its traditional uses and scientific advancements in understanding its pharmacological potential.

Keywords: *Caryota urens*, Fishtail palm, Medicinal properties, Traditional medicine, Pharmacological potential

INTRODUCTION

Caryota urens L. (English name: Fishtail palm, Bengali Flower is useful in gastric ulcer and migraine. Bark is name: Bonsupari) belongs to Arecaceae family. The plant used to treat rheumatic swellings and snake bite (Charles is a native of India, Myanmar and Sri lanka 2011; Uddin et al., 2015). Recent scientific 2015). Traditionally root is used to treat tooth ailments. investigations report that *C. urens* sap is nutritionally rich and contains mixture of simple sugars such as sucrose, glucose and fructose (Somasiri et al., 2008). Flavonoids have been isolated from the methanol extract of the fruits (Srivastav et al., 2015). The plant has been reported to possess significant antioxidant, anti-diabetic and anti-microbial activities in the last few years (Charles and Ramani, 2011; Ranasinghe et al., 2012; Krishnamoorthy et al., 2013; Azam et al., 2016; Wimalasiri et al., 2016; Sujitha and Kripa, 2018). In investigating Bangladesh medicinal plants (Sharmin et al., 2017-2018), the crude methanol extract of *C. urens* fruits in Bangladesh including its organic and aqueous soluble fractions was for the first

time evaluated for the antioxidant potential based on total phenolic content, phosphomolybdenum total antioxidant activity free radical scavenging activity, cytotoxic, thrombolytic, membrane stabilizing and antimicrobial properties.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant materials

Fruits of *C. urens* were obtained from Mirpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh. A voucher specimen (DACB-39528) is maintained in Bangladesh National Herbarium, Dhaka, Bangladesh for use in future.

The fruits (800 g) were dried under the sun and ground into powder. It was then macerated in 2.5 L of methanol for one week. It was filtered via fresh cotton bed and with Whatman filter paper number 1. It was concentrated with a rotary evaporator at low temperature and pressure. A modified version of Kupchan partition protocol (VanWagenen et al., 1993) was used to fractionate an aliquot (5 g) of the concentrated methanol extract; the partitionates obtained from there were evaporated to dryness with rotary evaporator. This yielded hexane soluble fraction (HXSF, 1.8 g), carbon tetrachloride soluble fraction CTCSF, 2.0 g), chloroform soluble fraction (CSF, 0.2 g) and aqueous soluble fraction (AQSF, 0.5 g). The residues were kept in a refrigerator for use later.

Total phenolic content

Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was used to determine the total phenolic content by Harbertson and Spayd (2006)'s method developed.

DPPH free radical scavenging assay

Brand-Williams et al. (1995)'s developed method was used to assess the capacity of the study samples to scavenge the stable 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) free radical. The positive controls were Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT) and ascorbic acid.

Phosphomolybdenum antioxidant assay

Phosphomolybdenum antioxidant assay method (Prieto et al., 1999) was used to evaluate the total antioxidant activity of the extract.

Brine shrimp lethality bioassay

This was done to determine the overall harmful activities of the dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) solutions of plant samples against *Artemia salina* in one day *in vivo* assay (Meyer et al., 1982). The positive control was Vincristine sulphate .

Thrombolytic activity

Prasad et al. (2006)'s method was used to evaluate the thrombolytic property. The positive control was streptokinase.

Membrane stabilizing activity

Omale and Okafor (2008)'s method was used to assess the membrane stabilizing property of the samples by analyzing their capacity to prevent hypotonic solution and heat-induced haemolysis of human erythrocytes.

Antimicrobial screening

Disc diffusion method was used to determine antimicrobial property (Bayer et al., 1966).

Statistical analysis

Three replicates of each sample were used for statistical analysis for all bioassays; the values are given as mean ± standard deviation (SD). A two-tailed Student's t-test was used to evaluate the results.

RESULTS

This research was done to analyze *C. urens* fruit extract for antioxidant, cytotoxic, thrombolytic, membrane stabilizing and antimicrobial activities.

The crude methanol extract of *C. urens* fruits have a high content of phenolic principles (106.88±0.19 mg of GAE/g of sample). The extract's total phenolic content and the free radical scavenging activity correlate positively (IC₅₀= 62.74±0.16 µg/m) (Table 1).

All the fractions had significant cytotoxic potential against *A. salina* in brine shrimp lethality bioassay. The crude methanol extract showed the highest cytotoxic activity with LC₅₀ value of 0.59±0.34 µg/mL in comparison to 0.451 µg/mL for Vincristine sulphate (Table 1).

C. urens extract had mild thrombolytic activity. The carbon tetrachloride soluble fraction was 20.48% of clot lysis in contrast to 66.77% clot lysis by streptokinase used as standard (Table 2).

At 1.0 mg/mL, *C. urens* samples protected the haemolysis of RBC caused by hypotonic solution and heat compared to the standard acetyl salicylic acid (0.10 mg/mL). The crude methanol extract prevented 64.17±0.26% of haemolysis of RBCs induced by hypotonic solution in contrast to 71.9% by acetyl salicylic acid (Table 2).

The antimicrobial activity of *C. urens* samples was analyzed against five gram positive and eight gram negative bacteria. The results were compared with ciprofloxacin, standard antibiotic. Among all the samples, the carbon tetrachloride soluble fractions against *Shigella* the largest zone of inhibition (13.0 mm) was displayed by dysenteriae (Table 3).

Table 1. Total phenolic content, phosphomolybdenum total antioxidant capacity, free radical scavenging and cytotoxic activities of *C. urens*.

Samples/ standards	Total phenolic content (mg of GAE/ g of dried extract)	Free radical scavenging activity IC ₅₀ (µg/mL)	Total antioxidant capacity (mg of ascorbic acid/100 g of extract)	Brine shrimp lethality bioassay LC ₅₀ (µg/mL)
ME	106.88±0.19	62.74±0.16	4.0±0.20	0.59±0.34
HXSF	1.45±0.25	387.74±0.46	1.12±0.27	0.71±0.53

CTCSF	7.48±0.18	120.24±0.09	4.0±0.38	3.11±0.12
AQSF	41.42±0.41	-	3.61±0.21	3.51±0.11
Ascorbic acid	-	5.8±0.21	-	-
BHT	-	27.5±0.54	-	-
Vincristine sulfate	-	-	-	0.451±0.04

Table 2. Thrombolytic and membrane stabilizing activities of *C. urens*.

% Inhibition of haemolysis

Samples/standards % of lysis of RBC

	Heat-induced		Hypotonic solution-induced	
ME	2.40±0.23	19.01±0.43	64.17±0.26	
HXSf	7.70±0.18	6.70±0.14	63.28±0.49	
CTCSF	20.48±0.44	10.00±0.27	60.91±0.54	
Water	3.79±0.21	-	-	
Streptokinase	66.77±0.36	-	-	
Hypotonic medium	-	-	-	
Acetyl salicylic acid	-	42.12±0.38	71.9±0.78	

ME = Methanolic crude extract; HXSf= Hexane soluble fraction; CTCSF = Carbon tetrachloride soluble fraction.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of *C. urens*.

Parameter	Diameter of zone of inhibition (mm)			
	ME	CTCSF	CSF	Ciprofloxacin
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	12.0±0.38	-	-	45.0±2.01
<i>B. megaterium</i>	-	-	-	42.0±1.17
<i>B. subtilis</i>	-	-	-	42.0±0.73
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	-	-	-	42.0±0.23
<i>Sarcina lutea</i>	-	-	8.0±0.12	42.0±0.56
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	-	-	-	42.0±0.43
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	-	-	-	42.0±1.11
<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	-	-	-	45.0±0.73
<i>S. paratyphi</i>	-	8.0±0.15	8.0±0.24	47.0±2.33
<i>Shigella boydii</i>	-	-	-	34.0±0.58
<i>S. dysenteriae</i>	-	13.0±0.39	-	42.0±0.22
<i>Vibrio mimicus</i>	8.0±0.22	8.0±0.18	8.0±0.41	40.0±0.45

V. parahaemolyticus - - - 35.0±0.44

ME = Methanolic crude extract; CTCSF = Carbon tetrachloride soluble fraction; CSF = Chloroform soluble fraction.

DISCUSSION

The high phenolic content of *C. urens* extract might contribute to its antioxidant potentials. Lupeol and ursolic acid have been isolated from the leaf of this plant (Muhaisen, 2013). Both compounds possess antioxidant potentials (Santiago et al., 2014; Tchimine et al., 2016). The antioxidant potential of *C. urens* extract might be due to the presence of these two compounds. Lupeol has been also found to be a potent cytotoxic component (Moriarity et al., 1998). Therefore, this compound might be responsible for the observed cytotoxic activity.

C. urens extract showed membrane stabilizing property. Leakage of serum proteins and fluid into the tissue causes inflammation. Membrane stabilizing property can prevent induction of inflammation (Chaitanya et al., 2011).

Ursolic acid possesses anti-inflammatory property (Checker et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2018). The presence of this compound in *C. urens* might contribute to the observed membrane stabilizing activity.

Conclusion

People have the common belief that nature is good. This belief has contributed to the increased popularity of traditional medicines. But consuming plant-based medicines might cause unwanted side effects because such medicines contain a large number of compounds with different activities. This study has revealed that *C. urens* fruit extract possesses significant antioxidant and membrane stabilizing potentials. Therefore, it is important to identify the compounds responsible for the observed activities from the fruit extract. Thus, the plant is a good candidate for further systematic, chemical and biological studies to isolate the active principles.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

REFERENCES

Azam S, Mahmud MK, Naquib MH, Hossain SM, Alam MN, Uddin MJ, Sajid I, Hossain MS, Karim MS, Hasan MA (2016). In vitro anti-oxidant and anti-microbial potentiality investigation of different fractions of *Caryota urens* leaves. *Biomedicines* 4(3): 17.

Bayer AW, Kirby WMM, Sherris JC, Turck M (1966). Antibiotic susceptibility testing by a standardized single disc method. *American Journal of Clinical Pathology* 45:493-496. https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcp/45.4_ts.493.

- Brand WW, Cuvelier M, Berset C (1995). Use of a free radical method to evaluate antioxidant activity. *LWT-Food science and Technology* 28(1): 25-30. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0023-6438\(95\)80008-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0023-6438(95)80008-5)
- Chaitanya R, Sandhya S, David B, Vinod KR, Murali S (2011). HRBC Membrane stabilizing property of root, stem and leaf of *Glochidion velutinum*. *International Journal of Research in Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Sciences* 2(1):256-259
- Charles A, Joseph M, Ramani VA (2011). Quantitative estimation of primary and secondary metabolites on flowers of *Caryota urens*. *International Journal of Applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology* 2(3):431-435.
- Charles A, Ramani VA (2011). Qualitative phytochemical screening, anti-oxidant and anti-microbial activity studies on ethanolic flowers extract of *Caryota urens* Linn. *International Journal of Applied Biology and Pharmaceutical Technology* 2:498-505.
- Checker R, Sandur SK, Sharma D, Patwardhan RS, Jayakumar S, Kohli V, Sethi G, Aggarwal BB, Sainis KB (2012). Potent anti-inflammatory activity of ursolic acid, a triterpenoid antioxidant, is mediated through suppression of NF- κ B, AP-1 and NF-AT. *PLoS One* 7(2):e31318. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0031318>
- Harbertson J, Spayd S (2006). Measuring phenolics in the winery. *American Journal of Enology and Viticulture* 57:280-288.
- Krishnamoorthy K, Senguttuvan J, Krishnaswamy T (2013). Evaluation of phytochemicals and in vitro antioxidant activities of some selected Indian medicinal fruits from Kannur city, Kerala. *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences* 2:4121-4138.
- Meyer BN, Ferringni NR, Puam JE, Lacobsen LB, Nichols DE, McLaughlin JL (1982). Brine shrimp: a convenient general bioassay for active constituents. *Planta Medica* 45:31-32. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2007-971236>
- Moriarity DM, Huang J, Yancey CA, Zhang P, Setzer WN, Lawton RO, Bates RB, Caldera S (1998). Lupeol is the cytotoxic principle in the leaf extract of *Dendropanax cf. querceti*. *Planta Medica* 64(4):370-372. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2006-957454>
- Muhaisen HMH (2013). Chemical constituents from the base leaves of *Caryota urens* (Palmae). *IOSR Journal of Applied Chemistry* 5(5):05-12.

Omale J, Okafor PN (2008). Comparative antioxidant capacity, membrane stabilization, polyphenols composition and cytotoxicity of the leaf and stem of *Cissus multistriata*. African Journal of Biotechnology 7:3129-3133.

Prasad S, Kashyap RS, Deopujari JY, Purohit HJ, Taori GM, Daginawala HF (2007). Effect of *Fagonia arabica* (Dhamasa) on in vitro thrombolysis. BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine 7:36. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6882-7-36>

Prieto P, Pineda M, Aguilar M (1999). Spectrophotometric quantitation of antioxidant capacity through the formation of a phosphomolybdenum complex: specific application to the determination of vitamin E. Analytical Biochemistry 269:337-341. <https://doi.org/10.1006/abio.1999.4019>.

Ranasinghe P, Premakumara GAS, Wijayarathna CD, Ratnasooriya WD (2012). Antioxidant activity of *Caryota urens* L. (Kithul) sap. Tropical Agricultural Research 23:117-125. <http://doi.org/10.4038/tar.v23i2.4643>.

Santiago LA, Dayrit KC, Correa PCB, Mayor ABR (2014). Comparison of antioxidant and free radical scavenging activity of triterpenesa-amyrin, oleanolic acid and ursolic acid. Journal of Natural Products 7 (2014):29-36

Somasiri HPPS, Premakumara GAS, Mahanama KRR (2008). Organic acids and free sugar composition of Kithul palm *Caryota urens* sap. Asian Symposium on Medicinal Plants, Spices and Other Natural Products (ASOMPS) XIII:125.

Sharmin T, Rahman MS, Mohammadi H (2018). Investigation of biological activities of the flowers of *Lagerstroemia speciosa*, the Jarul flower of Bangladesh. BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine 18:231. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12906-018-2286-6>.

Sharmin T, Rahman MS, Tahia F (2017). Investigation of biological activities of *Jasminum matthewii*. African Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology 11(3):38-44. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJPP2016.4697>.

Srivastav AK, Singh R, Manimegalai S, Rajeswari VD (2015) Identification of flavonoids in methanolic extract of *Caryota urens* (fish tail palm): a phytochemical screening involving structure analysis by FTIR spectroscopy. Research Journal of Phytochemistry 9:127-136. [10.3923/rjphyto.2015.127.136](https://doi.org/10.3923/rjphyto.2015.127.136).

Sujitha B, Kripa KG (2018). Comparative evaluation of antioxidant activity and liquid chromatography–Mass spectrometry-based phytochemical profiling of various biological parts of *Caryota urens*.

Pharmacognosy Magazine 14(59):665-672. 10.4103/pm.pm_320_18. Tchimene MK, Nwaehujor CO, Ezenwali M, Okoli CC, Iwu MM (2016). Free radical scavenging activity of lupeol isolated from the methanol leaf extract of *Crateva adansonii* Oliv. (Capparidaceae). International Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemical Research 8(3):419-426.

Uddin MS, Hasan MF, Mamun AA, Hossain MS, Islam T, Asaduzzaman M (2015). In-vitro estimation of antioxidant activity of *Caryota urens* fruits. INDO American Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences 2(11):1486-1490.

Van Wagenen BC, Larsen R, Cardellina JH II, Ranzazzo D, Lidert ZC, Swithenbank C (1993). Ulosantoin, a potent insecticide from the sponge *Ulosa ruetzleri*. The Journal of Organic Chemistry 58:335- 337. [https:// doi: 10.1021/jo00054a013](https://doi.org/10.1021/jo00054a013)

Wang Y, Li L, Deng S, Liu F, He Z (2018). Ursolic Acid Ameliorates Inflammation in Cerebral Ischemia and Reperfusion Injury Possibly via High Mobility Group Box 1/Toll-Like Receptor 4/NFκB Pathway. Frontiers in Neurology 9:253. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2018.00253.

Wimalasiri GEM, Ranasinghe P, Gunaratne DMA, Arachchi LPV (2016). Antioxidant and Anti-diabetic Properties of *Caryota Urens* (Kithul) Flour. Procedia Food Science 6:181-185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.profoo.2016.02.044>.